

Neural circuit mechanisms for continuous learning of distinct motor skills.

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The capacity of humans and animals to continuously acquire multiple motor skills without overwriting previously learned tasks is central to adaptive behaviours, yet most fundamental research addresses learning one skill at a time, leaving critical questions unanswered about how the brain consolidates and switches between different motor tasks. This project addresses that knowledge gap by investigating the neural circuits that underpin continuous learning of multiple distinct motor skills, an essential ability for biological organisms and a major challenge for artificial intelligence (AI) systems. In AI, continuous learning is notoriously difficult due to catastrophic forgetting (Kudithipudi et al., 2022), and insights from neuroscience could inspire solutions to this problem. Traditional learning theories describe multiple mechanisms for motor skill acquisition (e.g. error-based adaptation, reinforcement learning, habitual Hebbian processes) tied to distinct neural pathways (Krakauer et al., 2011; 2017). However, no unified framework explains how these pathways interact to maintain previously acquired skills while learning new ones. By combining cutting-edge neuroscience methods with machine learning techniques, this project will determine how brain network integration and stability support sequential motor skill learning without interference. Drawing on recent advances in neuroscience and AI (Bolaños, Xiao et al., 2021; Xiao et al., 2021; Xiao et al., 2017, 2023), we propose an interdisciplinary approach with three major aims:

Aim 1: Characterise brain-wide neural dynamics during sequential motor skill learning.

Aim 2: Identify fine-scale neuronal ensemble dynamics underlying motor skill encoding and retention.

Aim 3: Perform causal circuit manipulations to identify network components in learning and task switching.

I propose the Dynamic Stability in Network Integration (DSNI) hypothesis (**Figure 1**): continuous learning of distinct motor skills is achieved through a hybrid neural architecture that combines modular specialisation with globally integrated processes. Based on the DSNI hypothesis, I predict that certain “hub” regions, especially those at the interface of stable processing (e.g. sensorimotor cortex) and adaptive learning circuits (e.g. association cortex), will exhibit heightened meta-plasticity (the capacity for synaptic plasticity to be modulated) during sequential skill learning. This framework can be tested using neuroscience tools I have developed, such as Mesotrode, MesoNet, and MesoGAN (Xiao et al., 2017, 2023; Xiao et al., 2021; Xiao et al., 2025). Our behavioural experiments will examine how baseline skill proficiency and established network connectivity provide a stable backbone that accommodates rapid adaptation to new tasks. **Significance:** This research will advance our understanding of how the brain seamlessly acquires and retains multiple motor skills—an ability that is still only partially understood in neuroscience. By uncovering the neural principles that allow new tasks to be learned without displacing or degrading older skills, we address a fundamental question of neuroplasticity and memory: how does the brain strike a balance between stability and flexibility? These insights will fill a major knowledge gap in neuroscience, explaining the mechanisms of parallel memory storage and retrieval in different motor behaviours. Just as importantly, this project will glean into biological strategies for lifelong learning that can be adapted to address challenges in machine learning. Understanding how neural networks avoid catastrophic interference can inform the design of more efficient, flexible AI systems that learn continuously over time. In doing so, this interdisciplinary effort merging advanced neuroscience methods with state-of-the-art AI has the potential to catalyse a paradigm shift in fields ranging from cognitive neuroscience to adaptive robotics. Our findings may provide a roadmap for next-generation technologies that emulate the brain’s remarkable learning capacities. In the long term, the outcome of this project may enable innovative human-machine interfaces that allow seamless integration of new skills, fundamentally redefining learning in both brains and machines.

Innovation: This project employs a uniquely interdisciplinary approach, combining pioneering neuroscience technologies with advanced AI methods to address critical unresolved questions about continuous motor skill learning. I introduce the DSNI hypothesis as a unifying theory to test and explain how neural networks avoid overwriting previously learned skills. This research will integrate advanced tools I have developed: Mesotrode—an advanced chronic neural imaging system capable of simultaneously recording cortical and subcortical activity, MesoGAN—a generative adversarial network (GAN) to decode brain activity at the mesoscale, and MesoNet—an automated AI pipeline for analysing complex, large-scale neural datasets. Biological principles discovered here will be reciprocally applied to enhance AI, placing this project at the leading edge of research at the neuroscience–AI interface.

Background and preliminary data

A challenge in understanding sequential motor skill learning is capturing how large-scale neural circuits communicate, from single neurons to networks spanning cortical and subcortical regions, during ongoing behaviours. In the mammalian brain, local computations are frequently modulated by inputs from distant brain structures (Koch et al., 2016). While many studies have uncovered mechanisms for learning a single motor skill, very few have examined how

the brain can encode and preserve multiple skills in sequence without overwriting established representations. To address this complexity, my previous work has combined in vivo electrophysiology and wide-field imaging in behaving mice to map neuronal connectivity and investigate how neural dynamics evolve with behavioural states (Xiao et al., 2017). Single neurons' functional connectivity was shown to be highly state-dependent, coupling local microcircuits and broader cortical networks to meet task demands (Xiao et al., 2017; Clancy, et al., 2019; Peters, et al., 2021). Yet these early investigations only provided snapshots of connectivity, rather than chronic recordings capturing the learning of multiple tasks over time.

Building on these insights, I designed the Mesotrode (Xiao et al., 2023), a platform that integrates multi-site tetrode implants (Sepers et al., 2023) with mesoscale brain imaging (Silasi, Xiao et al., 2016; Xie, et al., 2016). This system preserves optical access to the entire dorsal cortex while enabling high-fidelity single-unit recordings in cortical and subcortical structures, allowing chronic characterisation of functional connectivity of

Figure 1 Mice continuously learn distinct motor skills

Dynamic Stability in Network Integration Hypothesis:

I propose that the brain's continuous learning capabilities are achieved through a hybrid neural architecture that combines **modular** specialization with **globally** integrated processes. It suggests that core neural processes (e.g. memory consolidation) remain relatively **stable** over time. However, the connections between modules and global networks are **adaptive**, allowing for rapid reconfiguration in response to new tasks. It involves a critical role for **inhibitory control** in maintaining the balance between stability and flexibility.

This system preserves optical access to the entire dorsal cortex while enabling high-fidelity single-unit recordings in cortical and subcortical structures, allowing chronic characterisation of functional connectivity of

individual cortical or subcortical neurons during distinct behavioural states (Zhang, Xiao et al., 2020) while preserving full optical access through a cranial window. Additionally, this platform allows simultaneous functional brain imaging and optogenetic manipulation across the dorsal cortex. Using this approach, I have found that neurons in various subcortical structures (hippocampus, thalamus, striatum, midbrain) display distinct connectivity patterns with the cortex during different behaviours (e.g. running vs. orofacial movements; Xiao et al., 2023). Notably, these patterns remain stable within a given behavioural state yet differ across brain regions, indicating each region has a consistent baseline pattern that can flexibly reconfigure for different motor functions. I also identified a previously undetected higher-order association cortical network involved in facial movement control that was confirmed through causal tests using optogenetic stimulation and inhibition (Xiao et al., 2023; Balbi, Xiao et al., 2021). These findings underscore the feasibility and power of combining optical imaging with targeted circuit perturbations to dissect functional pathways.

In parallel, I have developed analytical and computational tools to handle the complexity of multi-modal neural data. I created MesoNet (Xiao et al., 2021), an automated machine-learning pipeline for aligning and segmenting mesoscale fluorescence imaging data. MesoNet facilitates consistent region-of-interest identification across studies, which is crucial for comparing activity patterns as new tasks are learned. Using transgenic mice expressing fluorescent calcium indicators (e.g. GCaMP6), wide-field cortical imaging can reveal large-scale spatiotemporal neural activity patterns non-invasively (Silasi, Xiao et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2023), enabling high-throughput data collection and processing. To precisely relate neural activity to behaviour, quantitative analysis of movement is indispensable (Krakauer et al., 2017). Traditional measures such as reaction time or lever displacement capture only low-dimensional snapshots of performance. To overcome this limitation, I contributed to the development of a 3D virtual mouse model (**Figure 2**) that generates synthetic data for training AI-based behavioural classifiers (Bolaños, Xiao et al., 2021). This tool automates the extraction of detailed kinematic features, enabling the detection of subtle, high-dimensional behavioural variations. Furthermore, we established real-time, markerless tracking for selective body parts using deep learning (Forys, Xiao et al., 2018, 2020). By embedding motor actions into real-time auditory feedback loops, I recently demonstrated that continuous movement-coded auditory cues can accelerate motor skill learning (Xiao and Balbi, 2025). These findings indicate the potential of closed-loop approaches that shape motor skill learning through immediate sensorimotor feedback, laying the groundwork for next-generation brain-machine interfaces.

Figure 2 A realistic mouse body model for 3D motion capture. A) Creation of the 3D model, starting with high resolution CT scans. Rigging of the model using the skeleton shown in the CT scans as guides. B) Creation of animations based on real videos. C) Single-camera 2D-to-3D pose lifting using a linear neural network. D) Comparison of 2D and 3D poses generated by the pose lifter. Different colours in the t-SNE plot indicate different pose clusters.

Building on this, my research aims to uncover the mechanisms of continuous motor learning by: characterising brain-wide neural and behavioural dynamics (**Aim 1**), investigating fine-scale neuronal ensemble activity (**Aim 2**), and identifying network components in learning and task switching (**Aim 3**).

Experimental Plan

To elucidate the neural mechanisms underpinning sequential motor skill learning, I will employ transgenic GCaMP6 mice that express a fluorescent calcium indicator, thereby allowing real-time visualisation of neuronal activity across brain regions. These mice will be systematically trained on a series of increasingly complex motor tasks specifically designed to probe and challenge distinct sensorimotor pathways, ranging from rudimentary activities like running to more complex behaviours such as handling and reaching. My experimental pipeline will integrate a suite of advanced imaging modalities already available in the lab (Wang et al., 2023; Xiao and Balbi, 2025) including wide-field calcium imaging for large-scale cortical activity mapping and two-photon microscopy for high-resolution examination of specific neuronal ensembles. I will also employ optogenetic tools to selectively activate or silence targeted circuit elements, causally testing their contributions to learning and execution of multiple tasks. By matching neural activity to detailed behavioural assessments, this approach will provide unprecedented insights into how individual brain regions and ensembles dynamically adapt to accommodate sequential motor skill learning.

Aim 1: Characterise brain-wide neural and behavioural dynamics during sequential motor skill learning.

Rationale: While single-task motor learning has been extensively studied, how the brain integrates and retains multiple skills remains poorly understood. A comprehensive, multimodal dataset capturing neural and behavioural dynamics as mice sequentially acquire distinct motor skills is needed to provide a network-level perspective on how different brain regions collaborate during sequential learning. By introducing tasks of increasing complexity (running, string-pulling, reaching), I will examine how neural circuits transition between skills, test for network stability and flexibility, and identify key regions that coordinate sequential motor skill learning.

Hypothesis: I hypothesise that distinct neural circuits are selectively engaged for each motor task and dynamically reconfigure upon learning new skills. This adaptive reconfiguration is critical for simultaneous retention of previously acquired skills and preventing interference or overwriting. I further hypothesise that interconnected cortical and subcortical networks underlie transitions between tasks, with measurable shifts in connectivity correlating with improved motor performance.

Experiment 1.1: Establish baseline motor skill proficiency and corresponding neural activity.

Transgenic GCaMP6 mice ($n=16$ mice, 8 male, 8 female) will undergo increasingly complex motor training in a head-fixed setup, the core elements of which include the recording component of the Mesotrode (Xiao et al., 2023), multiple synchronised cameras, waterspout. Mice will learn a wheel-running task without explicit rewards, allowing self-motivated exploration and establishing baseline skill metrics such as running duration and speed. Next, animals will transition to a string-pulling task with gradually increasing resistance, and finally to a reaching-for-water task. To control for potential order effects, a separate cohort of mice will train on the tasks in reverse sequence ($n=16$ mice) with an additional a non-trained control group ($n=16$ mice). During each phase, I will use multi-angle, synchronized high-speed video to record fine-grained behavioural parameters—such as running periodicity, pulling efficiency, or reach-to-grasp trajectories—and correlate them with neural signals. Mice will receive the Mesotrode implant consisting of a chronic wide-field window and recording tetrodes (Xiao et al., 2023) to capture simultaneous wide-field calcium

Figure 3 Left: Simultaneous wide-field calcium imaging and 3D paw tracking during mouse reaching for water task. Right: Cortex-wide calcium dynamics during reaching for water motor task training. Top images are averaged cortical activation of all the trials for each day.

imaging (cortex) and multi-site electrophysiology (hippocampus, thalamus, striatum, cerebellum, and midbrain), providing a detailed view of both cortical and subcortical activity to identify the engagement of distinct neural circuits corresponding to each motor skill. By establishing baseline neural connectivity prior to training and tracking its evolution, I will identify how different brain regions adapt their functional interactions as new tasks are learned. The neural activity will be analysed in relation to specific behavioural outputs to create a detailed map of brain-behaviour relationships (**Figure 3**).

Experiment 1.2: Characterise neural circuit engagement during task performance.

Real-time calcium imaging and cellular electrophysiology data will be matched to 3D behavioural data, enabling us to align precise motor events (e.g., pulling onset, successful reach) with neural dynamics. Dimensionality reduction techniques (e.g., t-SNE, PCA) will help visualise and categorise network states associated with specific tasks or transitions between tasks (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4 A) Set up of wide-field calcium imaging. B) Brain to atlas registration pipeline. C) Classification of brain activity motifs. D) Averaged cortical motifs for each cluster.

Figure 5 MesoGAN, a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) tailored to generate realistic behavioural videos from neural decoding of mesoscopic cortical calcium dynamics. Up: Diagram of GAN framework with soft attention mechanism. Bottom: Example fake videos generated from mesoscale calcium dynamics. Attention maps (overlaid on the brain) pinpoint predictive brain activity features that encode specific movements.

To determine whether learning-related signals are confined to localised modules or distributed across widespread circuits, I will apply clustering algorithms and advanced machine learning approaches. I will also use previously developed computational models such as MesoGAN (**Figure 5**) to simulate body movement during sequential motor skill learning from neural decoding of brain-wide network dynamics. MesoGAN also allows me to create visual representations such as attention maps to identify predictive patterns associated with distinct motor tasks. Together, these analyses will reveal how ensembles adjust over time and whether stable circuit motifs, recurring patterns of neuronal activity, emerge when shifting from one skill to another.

Outcomes: **Aim 1** will produce a comprehensive **multimodal, multiscale** dataset of neural and behavioural changes during sequential task learning. By mapping the evolution of cortical–subcortical networks as new skills are learned, I will build a quantitative framework for identifying key circuit mechanisms that support sequential motor skill learning. These data will serve as the basis for a platform to guide the investigation of neuronal ensembles in **Aim 2** and causal circuit tests in **Aim 3**.

Aim 2: Identify fine-scale neuronal ensemble dynamics underlying motor skills encoding and retention.

Rationale: While **Aim 1** will shed light on how different brain regions collaborate during sequential motor skill learning, it remains unclear which specific neuronal ensembles within these regions encode and preserve individual motor skills. Achieving single-neuron resolution in vivo will allow us to determine how distinct subsets of excitatory and inhibitory cells contribute to skill-specific representations and whether these representations persist or reorganise as new skills are acquired. By tracking the fine-scale dynamics of identified cell populations over time, **Aim 2** will clarify how motor skills are robustly stored and updated without overwriting previously learned actions.

Hypothesis: I hypothesise that distinct but partially overlapping ensembles encode each motor skill at high resolution. Within these ensembles, stable “anchor” neurons will facilitate retention of established skills, while more adaptive neurons will exhibit dynamic reconfiguration to accommodate newly learned tasks. I also hypothesise that these dynamics differ between primary sensorimotor and higher-order association cortices, reflecting variations in local plasticity and global integrative function.

Experiment 2.1: Two-photon imaging in sensorimotor cortex.

Building on **Aim 1**’s network-level findings, I will surgically implant a chronic cranial window over the sensorimotor cortex of GCaMP6 mice ($n = 16$), allowing for repeated two-photon imaging sessions (**Figure 6**) spanning the acquisition and retention of the same battery of motor tasks used in **Aim 1**. By tracking over time, the cortical activity patterns that are activated during the motor tasks in the primary motor cortex at the microcircuit level, I will map the emergence, persistence and evolution of skill-specific representations.

Figure 6 Decoding behavioral states from neuronal ensembles using two-photon imaging.

To dissect the stability and flexibility of these ensembles, I will compare mice undergoing standard training to two additional groups: a non-trained control cohort ($n = 16$) to assess baseline or “idle” ensemble dynamics, and a cohort trained in reverse task order ($n = 16$) to control for sequence effects. Neuronal segmentation and calcium transient analyses will reveal whether a consistent subset of neurons maintains core motor representations, while other neurons flexibly shift their tuning to accommodate new skills.

Experiment 2.2: Two-photon imaging in association cortex.

In parallel, another group of GCaMP6 expressing mice ($n = 16$) will undergo the same training regimen while imaging a higher-order association cortex identified in **Aim 1** as a potential “hub” for sequential motor skill learning. By comparing neuronal ensemble plasticity across sensorimotor and association cortices, I will determine whether higher-order areas exhibit distinct patterns of stability and adaptation. The same control groups (no training and reverse training) will be used to disentangle skill-specific changes from generic learning or reordering effects. This design will help clarify whether association cortex acts as a meta-plasticity interface, as posited by the DSNI hypothesis, mediating the integration and retention of diverse motor skills.

Outcomes: **Aim 2** will reveal the microcircuit mechanisms that allow individual neurons and ensembles to sustain multiple motor skills in parallel. By correlating fine-scale neural data with the broad network findings from **Aim 1**, I will build a multi-level account of sequential motor skill learning, from single-cell plasticity to large-scale circuit reorganisation. This evidence will be crucial for identifying the specific targets I will manipulate in **Aim 3** to test causality and further refine our understanding of how the brain seamlessly handles sequential motor skill acquisition.

Aim 3: Causal circuit manipulation to identify network components in learning and task switching.

Rationale: **Aims 1** and **Aim 2** will identify cortical and subcortical regions engaged in sequential learning, but proof direct causal evidence of their roles requires targeted manipulation. In **Aim 3**, I will employ transgenic mice expressing Channelrhodopsin-2 under a vesicular γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) transporter promoter (VGAT-ChR2) to selectively inhibit neurons in sensorimotor cortex and higher-order association areas (e.g., secondary motor cortex (M2), parietal association cortex (PTA)) identified in earlier aims. By transiently silencing neuronal activity with light delivered through the Mesotrode’s chronic wide-field window, I will determine whether reduced neuronal output in each targeted region disrupts or modulates sequential task performance. Control groups lacking functional opsin expression or light stimulation will ensure the observed effects are specifically due to optogenetic stimulation rather than procedural artifacts. I will also test subsets of mice that receive continuous, movement-coded auditory feedback to test if external cues mitigate or exacerbate performance deficits caused by reduced circuit excitability.

Hypothesis: I hypothesise that: 1. Inhibiting sensorimotor regions (e.g., primary motor cortex) during acquisition or execution of a newly introduced task will compromise skill acquisition and retention of old skills. 2. Inhibiting association cortices (e.g., M2, PTA) will either impair skill switching (if these regions serve as integrative hubs) or possibly reduce interference (if overactive excitatory circuits cause conflict between old and new skills). 3. Movement-coded auditory feedback will partially rescue performance when inhibitory perturbations are mild or strategically timed, shedding light on the interconnectivity between top-down circuit modulation and bottom-up sensory reinforcement.

Experiment 3.1: Inhibition in sensorimotor cortex during sequential skill acquisition.

I will train transgenic VGAT-ChR2 mice ($n = 16$) to perform a sequence of two tasks: string-pulling and reaching-for-water. Optogenetic inhibition during the transition phase between tasks will assess whether reducing excitatory output disrupts the incorporation of novel motor actions or destabilizes previously acquired skills. Control mice ($n = 16$) will undergo identical procedures without active opsin expression or light stimulus.

Experiment 3.2: Inhibition in association cortex to examine skill switching.

A separate cohort of VGAT-ChR2 mice ($n = 16$), will undergo inhibition of excitatory neurons in higher-order association areas (e.g., M2, PTA)—regions hypothesized to coordinate transitions between tasks. This will assess whether these regions facilitate skill transitions or endogenous excitatory activity interferes with task switching. Control groups will be included as previously detailed. This experiment is key to testing the DSNI hypothesis that adaptive learning circuits require a precise balance of excitatory drive to merge new and old skill representations.

Experiment 3.3: Timing and closed-loop inhibition.

Leveraging the Mesotrode’s real-time electrophysiological readouts, I will implement closed-loop optogenetic stimulation triggered by neural events or discrete behavioural states in mice ($n = 32$). For example, detection of specific cortical-subcortical oscillations or spiking ensembles linked to task switching in aims 1 and 2 may be used to trigger a brief stimulation pulse. Comparing outcomes between event-timed vs. continuous stimulation will elucidate whether precisely timed silencing can “short-circuit” maladaptive states or hamper beneficial plasticity. A subset of these mice ($n = 16$) will also receive continuous auditory feedback (Xiao and Balbi, 2025) (**Figure 7**) to test whether external feedback can recapitulate the role of the circuits targeted for inhibition and shape sequential task performance.

Outcomes: Aim 3 will establish how reducing excitatory activity in sensorimotor, association, or subcortical circuits alters sequential motor skill learning and retention, identifying brain components that actively enable the “dynamic stability” that allows sequential learning. Control groups and auditory feedback conditions will disentangle the causal role of the dynamic neuronal patterns targeted by inhibitory perturbations. Collectively, these findings will confirm or refine the DSNI hypothesis by identifying crucial nodes that, when inhibited, disrupt sequential task learning and integration. This will inform interventions for optimising skill learning in humans and AI-based adaptive systems.

Figure 7. Real-time tracking system for continuous movement coded auditory feedback during reaching task. A. Schematic diagram of the closed-loop system integrating real-time pose estimation and auditory feedback. **B.** Left: An example image showing real-time tracking of the forepaw digits. Right: Time series plots of the auditory tone frequency (green), left paw (red) and right paw (black) vertical displacement.

Feasibility and risk management: This project leverages my expertise in multimodal neural recording, AI-driven analysis (MesoNet, MesoGAN) and optogenetic circuit interrogation. The Mesotrode platform, wide-field calcium imaging and two-photon microscopy are already established in the Balbi lab at the University of Queensland, ensuring the feasibility of acquiring high-resolution neural data. Collaborations with computational neuroscientists and AI experts will streamline the analysis of extensive neural and behavioural datasets. Collectively, these measures provide a high likelihood of success for achieving the project’s aims. All data will be analysed with a rigorous, integrative approach: I will apply both classical statistical analyses and advanced machine learning to large neural and behavioural datasets, ensuring I detect subtle effects and individual variability with high confidence. This comprehensive experimental plan is designed to be immediately feasible—it capitalizes on techniques and equipment already in hand—and sufficiently ambitious to generate new knowledge at the frontier of neuroscience and AI.

Sample sizes and statistical power calculations: Based on pilot data and effect sizes observed in our previous studies (Xiao et al., 2017, 2021, 2023, 2025), each experimental group will include approximately 16 animals (male and female), providing 80% power to detect meaningful differences in behavioural and neural measures. Comparisons will be evaluated using standard parametric tests (e.g., Student’s t-tests, ANOVAs) or non-parametric equivalents when assumptions are unmet. In addition, more advanced machine learning classifiers and dimensionality reduction techniques will enhance detection of subtle effects in large-scale, multimodal datasets. This balanced approach ensures both adequate statistical power and nuanced analyses of inter-group and inter-individual variability.

BENEFIT

This project aims to elucidate how the brain continuously learns and retains multiple motor skills without disruptive interference—a critical unresolved question in neuroscience. By identifying neural mechanisms responsible for

balancing stable memory retention and flexible adaptation, this research will significantly deepen our understanding of neuroplasticity and memory consolidation. Outcomes from this work will reveal specific neural ensembles and network states that allow the brain to continuously learn new motor tasks without erasing previously acquired skills, a first step for the development of technology for augmented skill learning at the workplace and recovery of function in patients with reduced mobility. By understanding how the brain achieves this dynamic stability, we can also develop biologically inspired strategies for AI systems, directly addressing the longstanding AI challenge of catastrophic forgetting. Practical implications include improving the adaptability of AI-driven systems in autonomous robotics, enabling rapid behavioural adjustments with reduced computational overhead. In sectors such as sustainable manufacturing, these innovations could significantly lower energy costs and minimize downtime, facilitating continuous machine adaptability. Over the next 5 years, foundational insights could yield energy-efficient, continuously updating AI prototypes that prioritize adaptability. Over a 20-year horizon, such biologically grounded strategies should significantly enhance Australia's global competitiveness in industries dependent on advanced neuroscience and AI technologies, benefiting education, healthcare, and environmental management.

References:

1. Balbi, M., Xiao, D., Jativa Vega, M., Hu, H., Vanni, M. P., Bernier, L.-P., LeDue, J. M., MacVicar, B. A., & Murphy, T. H. (2021). Gamma frequency activation of inhibitory neurons in the acute phase after stroke attenuates vascular and behavioral dysfunction. *Cell Reports*, *34*(5), 108696. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2021.108696>
2. Bolaños, L. A., Xiao, D., LeDue, J. M., Gupta, P., Doebeli, C., Ford, N. L., Hu, H., Rhodin, H., & Murphy, T. H. (2021). A three-dimensional virtual mouse generates synthetic training data for behavioral analysis. *Nature Methods*, *18*(4), 378–381. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01103-9>
3. Clancy, K. B., Orsolich, I., & Mrcic-Flogel, T. D. (2019). Locomotion-dependent remapping of distributed cortical networks. *Nature Neuroscience*, *22*(5), 778–786. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41593-019-0357-8>
4. Forys, B. J., Xiao, D., Gupta, P., & Murphy, T. H. (2018). Real-time markerless video tracking of body parts in mice using deep neural networks. *bioRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/482349>
5. Forys, B. J., Xiao, D., Gupta, P., & Murphy, T. H. (2020). Real-time selective markerless tracking of forepaws of head-fixed mice using deep neural networks. *eNeuro*, *7*(3), Article ENEURO.0096-20.2020. <https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0096-20.2020>
6. Koch, C., Massimini, M., Boly, M., & Tononi, G. (2016). Neural correlates of consciousness: Progress and problems. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, *17*(5), 307–321. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn.2016.22>
7. Krakauer, J. W., & Mazzoni, P. (2011). Human sensorimotor learning: Adaptation, skill, and beyond. *Current Opinion in Neurobiology*, *21*(4), 636–644. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conb.2011.06.012>
8. Krakauer, J. W., Ghazanfar, A. A., Gomez-Marín, A., MacIver, M. A., & Poeppel, D. (2017). Neuroscience needs behavior: Correcting a reductionist bias. *Neuron*, *93*(3), 480–490. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2016.12.041>
9. Kudithipudi, D., Aguilar-Simon, M., Babb, J., Bazhenov, M., Blackiston, D., Bongard, J., Brna, A. P., Raja, S. C., Cheney, N., Clune, J., Feldman, D. E., Friston, K., Grcic, M., Gupta, A., Ha, S., Kao, J. C., Ketz, N. A., Kording, K. P., Levin, M., ... Siegelmann, H. T. (2022). Biological underpinnings for lifelong learning machines. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, *4*(3), 196–210. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-022-00452-0>
10. Peters, A. J., Fabre, J. M. J., Steinmetz, N. A., Harris, K. D., & Carandini, M. (2021). Striatal activity topographically reflects cortical activity. *Nature*, *591*(7850), 420–425. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-03166-8>
11. Sepers, M. D., Mackay, J. P., Koch, E. T., Xiao, D., Mohajerani, M. H., Chan, A. W., Smith-Dijak, A. I., Ramandi, D., & Murphy, T. H. (2022). Altered cortical processing of sensory input in Huntington disease mouse models. *Neurobiology of Disease*, *169*, 105740. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbd.2022.105740>
12. Silasi, G., Xiao, D., Vanni, M. P., Chen, A. C. N., & Murphy, T. H. (2016). Intact skull chronic windows for mesoscopic wide-field imaging in awake mice. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods*, *267*, 141–149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneumeth.2016.04.012>
13. Wang, C., Lin, C., Zhao, Y., Samantzis, M., Sedlak, P., Sah, P., & Balbi, M. (2023). 40-Hz optogenetic stimulation rescues functional synaptic plasticity after stroke. *Cell Reports*, *42*(12), 113475. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2023.113475>
14. Wang, Y., Sepers, M. D., Xiao, D., Raymond, L. A., & Murphy, T. H. (2023). Water-reaching platform for longitudinal assessment of forelimb motor function and recovery in mice. *eNeuro*, *10*(1), Article ENEURO.0452-22.2022. <https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0452-22.2022>
15. Xie, Y., Chan, A. W., McGirr, A., Xue, S., Xiao, D., Zeng, H., & Murphy, T. H. (2016). Resolution of high-frequency mesoscale intracortical maps using the genetically encoded glutamate sensor iGluSnFR. *Journal of Neuroscience*, *36*(4), 1261–1272. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2744-15.2016>
16. Xiao, D., & Balbi, M. (2025). Continuous auditory feedback promotes fine motor skill learning in mice. *eNeuro*, *12*(3), Article ENEURO.0008-25.2025. <https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0008-25.2025>
17. Xiao, D., Forys, B. J., Vanni, M. P., & Murphy, T. H. (2021). MesoNet allows automated scaling and segmentation of mouse mesoscale cortical maps using machine learning. *Nature Communications*, *12*(1), Article 5992. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-26255-2>
18. Xiao, D., Vanni, M. P., Mitelut, C. C., Chan, A. W., LeDue, J. M., Xie, Y., & Murphy, T. H. (2017). Mapping cortical mesoscopic networks of single spiking cortical or sub-cortical neurons. *eLife*, *6*, e19976. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.19976>
19. Xiao, D., Yan, Y., & Murphy, T. H. (2023). Mesotrode allows chronic simultaneous mesoscale cortical imaging and subcortical or peripheral nerve spiking activity recording in mice. *eLife*, *12*, e87691. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.87691>
20. Zhang, M., Xiao, D., Murphy, T. H., Poline, J.-B., & Evans, A. C. (2020). Group-patch based classification and asymptotic predicting imbalanced neuron spikes. In *2020 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)* (pp. 1–6). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IJCNN48605.2020.9207011>